

SOME THEORETICAL VIEWS ON POVERTY ERADICATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the essence of poverty, its causes, definition of poverty criteria, as well as ways to reduce poverty in our country in the context of a pandemic.

Keywords: Poverty, poverty reduction, poverty criterion, pandemic, poverty line.

Research by the World Bank shows that pandemic-related job losses around the world have hit the already poor and vulnerable hardest. At the same time, this pandemic has partially changed the state of global poverty by creating millions of “new poor”.

The preliminary analysis included in the World Bank report shows that the new poor are some who live in cities, are better educated, and work in agriculture, making up fewer of those who lived in extreme poverty before COVID-19. These results are important for policies to improve the quality of life and reduce poverty. It shows how some countries can implement swift, flexible policies to overcome crises, protect the most vulnerable, and promote sustainable recovery.¹

In his address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan stated that the ultimate goal of economic reforms in the new year is to reduce poverty and increase the welfare of the population. It is planned to achieve these strategic goals at the expense of high economic growth that creates equal

¹ World Bank reference. Poverty and shared prosperity 2020: Reversals of fortune.
<https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/poverty-and-shared-prosperity>

opportunities for all, and with this in mind, comprehensive work will be carried out in 2021.¹

It is worth noting that currently there is no generally accepted and unified definition of the concept of poverty worldwide. Each country defines poverty based on its own poverty line.

According to Professor M. Muhammedov, "Poor population can be defined in two categories. The first category is poor population - those who do not want to improve their lives, but are too lazy to try to do it." The second category is people who have become like this due to certain reasons, who want to work, but for some reasons, they cannot do it².

According to Professor M.Pardaev, "Poverty people can be divided into three groups. The first is the unemployed, people who have appropriate qualifications but cannot find a decent job. The second category includes persons who are employed, but their monthly salary is not enough to lift their family out of the poverty line. The third is the segment of the population that does not have the opportunity to work (disabled, unable to work, children and the elderly without a supporter)³.

In our opinion, the second approach is more inclusive of the concept of poverty. Because at present there is a segment of the population that cannot provide enough for their families by receiving low wages.

In addition, according to the methodology proposed by the World Bank as a result of research conducted in 115 countries in 2015, the poverty line for all countries according to purchasing power parity at 2011 prices is 1.9, and the poverty line is 1 based on the low, middle and high-income levels of the population of the countries. ,9; 3.2; It is recommended to set it at 5.5 and 21.7 USD.

Poverty assessment requires several well-defined skills and techniques. Poverty, in general, is a relative concept. Some consider themselves poor because they don't have rest in the most prestigious places abroad, while others are called poor because they don't have shelter and food for their saddles.

According to recognized views, poverty is determined by three levels: absolute poverty, relative poverty, and subjective poverty.

People living in absolute poverty can only meet the minimum needs that ensure biological survival. The extreme poverty line is set at \$1 per day based on the ability to purchase products, while the poverty line is set at \$1.9 per day. In the European Union, the relatively poor are those who earn less than 60% of the average salary in

¹ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev to the Oliy Majlis dated December 29, 2020.

² Muhammedov M. (2020) People living on less than 1.9 USD // "Zarafshon" newspaper. June 23, 2020. 68 numbers. Page 2.

³ Pardaev M.Q., Pardaev O. Ways to assess poverty and reduce it. Treatise. Samarkand, 2020

the country. A subjective assessment of poverty is people's own assessment of their material well-being. In short, poverty is the inability to provide a certain acceptable standard of living for a certain person

Uzbekistan is among the countries with average income according to the indicator of national income per capita (average of 1533 US dollars per person per year). \$3.2 per person per day is the average poverty line. For countries with higher than average national income, \$5.5 per person per day is the average poverty line.

According to the World Bank, 736 million people (10 percent of the population) live in extreme poverty (having an income of less than \$1.9 a day), and almost half of the world's population - 3.4 billion people - have an income of less than \$5.5 a day. The continent with the highest level of poverty is Africa, the poorest countries on the planet are the Democratic Republic of the Congo (extreme poverty level - 77.1 percent) and Madagascar (77.6 percent).

To sum up, reducing poverty depends not only on economic factors, but also on a person's inner spiritual worldview, and no reform can bring a person out of poverty if a person does not change his worldview.

REFERENCES:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the measures of fundamental renewal of the State policy on economic development and poverty reduction" No. PF-5975. 26.03.2020.
2. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev to the Oliy Majlis dated December 29, 2020.
3. World Bank reference. Poverty and shared prosperity 2020: Reversals of fortune. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/poverty-and-shared-prosperity>
4. Pardaev M.Q., Pardaev O. Ways to assess poverty and reduce it. Treatise. Samarkand, 2020.
5. Muhammedov M. (2020) People living on less than 1.9 USD // "Zarafshon" newspaper. June 23, 2020. 68 numbers. Page 2.
6. Shadieva, G. M., & o'g'li Isoqulov, Z. S. (2022). WAYS TO REDUCE POVERTY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 957-962.
7. Mardievna, S. G., & Zhamshedovich, K. Z. (2023). THE ROLE OF FAMILY BUSINESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SERVICE INDUSTRY. *Thematics Journal of Commerce and Management*, 7(1).
8. Shodiyeva, G., Tog'ayeva, D. A., & Sul'tonov, B. A. (2022). KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI IQTISODIYOTDA TUTGAN O'RNI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(5), 610-613.

9. Shadiyeva, G. (2022). The Role of Family Business in the Development of the Service Industry. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 5(9), 213-218.
10. Shadieva, G. M., & Akbarovna, K. S. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF " FAMILY ECONOMY", ITS DEVELOPMENT. *Journal of new century innovations*, 20(3), 32-41.
11. Mardiyevna, S. G., & Oblokulovich, K. S. (2021). Methodology for determining the role of family business in the economy. *European Business and Management*, 7(6), 199.
12. Mardiyevna, S. G., & Anvarovna, E. D. (2022). MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF FAMILY BUSINESSES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 206-211.
13. Shadieva, G., & Shakirova, F. (2020). MILLIY INNOVATSION TIZIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA VA INNOVATSIYALARNING O 'RNI. SCIENCE AND INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT, (4), 9-16.
14. Пардаев, М. Қ., & Шодиева, Г. М. (2001). Оила хўжалиги иқтисодиёти ва тадбиркорлиги. Самарқанд, СамКИ, 151.
15. Shadieva, G. M. (2022). SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONCEPT OF "FAMILY ECONOMY". *Confrencea*, 1(1), 239-243.
16. Boliboev A. A. et al. METHODS OF PLANNING PRODUCTION PROCESSES //GospodarkaiInnowacje. – 2022. – Т. 24. – С. 961-964.
17. Yazdonov Q. G., Ubaydullayev B. S., Mirzaeva S. N. THE PROBLEM OF ORGANIZING THE WORKPLACE AT THE ENTERPRISE //GospodarkaiInnowacje. – 2022. – Т. 24. – С. 982-985.
18. Djaborovna P. D. et al. Opportunities for Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship Development in Rural Areas //American Journal of Economics and Business Management. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 6. – С. 141-145.
19. Uktamova D. B., Ubaydullayev B. S., Mirzaeva S. N. Factors of Improving the Organization of Labor at the Enterprise //Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 88-91.
20. Nortojiev M. A., Ubaydullayev B. S., Mirzaeva S. N. On the Issue of Certification of Workplaces According to Working Conditions //Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 94-96.
21. Hamitov S. I., Ubaydullayev B. S., Mirzaeva S. N. Organization of Staff Work at the Enterprise //Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 97-100.

22. Nodirovna M. S., Faxriddinovich U. F., Dusmurotovich U. M. Ways and Prospects for Developing the System of Residential Services in Rural Areas, Increasing Employment //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 17. – C. 96-101.
23. Zugurova Z. D., Ubaydullayev B. S. and Mirzaeva S. N. (2022). EFFICIENT PLANNING OF PRODUCTION PROCESSES. International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics, [online] pp.416–418.
24. Yakhyoyeva S. O., Ubaydullayev B. S.. and Mirzaeva S. N. (2022). FEATURES OF THE DIVISION AND COOPERATION OF LABOR AT THE ENTERPRISE. International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics, [online] pp.413–415.
25. Mamayunusovich, P. O., & Nodirovna, M. S. (2022). Management of the Mechanism of Storage and Sale of Products in the Republic of Uzbekistan. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 2(5), 67–71.
26. Saidakhmedovich, S. T. ., Nodirovna, M. S. ., &Khaydarjanovna, S. D. . (2022). Ways to Improve the Performance of Service Enterprises in Rural Areas. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 24, 21-24.
27. M.S.Nodirovna, Shaptakov and Mamasoliyevna, K.C. (2022). Improving the Economic Impact of Increasing Foreign Investment in Uzbekistan in the Digital Economic Environment. AcademicJournalofDigitalEconomicsandStability, [online] 16, pp.160–165
28. M.S. Nodirovna, Ta'nakulovich, T.K. and Baxtiyorovich, S.J. (2022). WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. GospodarkaiInnowacje., [online] 22, pp.182–186.